

Effects of Zn²⁺ concentrations on rate^a of twin seedlings germination percentage^b in 3 varieties.

Zn ²⁺ concn (M)	Shuang 3 (indica)		Shuang 13 (indica)		Lu 52 (japonica)	
	Twin seedling rate (%)	Germination (%)	Twin seedling rate (%)	Germination (%)	Twin seedling rate (%)	Germination (%)
Control	30.9	90.3	3.3	81.0	4.5	72.9
1 × 10 ⁻⁶	33.2	82.3	6.6	80.7	5.4	77.2
1 × 10 ⁻⁵	41.8	90.1	6.8	77.8	7.0	76.0
1 × 10 ⁻⁴	34.7	90.7	6.0	82.1	5.9	77.8
1 × 10 ⁻³	31.4	87.9	4.5	86.6	5.1	80.6
1 × 10 ⁻²	34.0	92.7	5.0	74.3	6.1	72.3
1 × 10 ⁻¹	0	0	0	0	0	0

^aNumber of twin seedlings (including triplets) ÷ no. of total seeds × 100. ^b(Number of twin seedlings + no. of single seedlings) ÷ no. of total seeds × 100.

The optimum concentration of Zn²⁺ was 1 × 10⁻⁵ M, at which the twin seedlings frequency of Shuang 3 increased by 10.9%. The twin seedling rate of Shuang 13 increased by 3.5% and that of Lu 52, 2.5% (see table). The results also indicated that Zn²⁺ concentrations of 1 × 10⁻¹ M restricted seedling development.

Zn²⁺ increases the twin seedling rate because it is related to the synthesis of IAA and protein and stimulates N metabolism. □

Restorers and maintainers for five CMS lines

S. B. Pradhan, S. N. Ratho, and P. J. Jachuck, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India

Isolation of restorers and maintainers for different cytoplasmic-genetic male sterile (CMS) lines is important to develop appropriate hybrid combinations and new CMS lines for hybrid rice breeding programs.

Twenty-one locally adapted, high-yielding elite breeding lines were used as pollen parents for crossing five CMS lines developed at CRRRI (Kiran A,

Krishna A, Deepa A, Madhuri A [WA source], and Krishna A [Kalinga-I source]). We randomly collected anthers from 10-15 spikelets of three panicles from individual F₁ plants during anthesis. They were examined under a microscope using Lugol's iodine solution; pollen sterility was estimated. Spikelet fertility was estimated on two to three panicles that had been bagged on each of the hybrid plants.

Varieties were classified as effective restorers (spikelet fertility more than 80%), partial restorer (spikelet fertility 25-79%), weak maintainers (spikelet fertility less than 25%), and effective

maintainers (spikelet fertility less than 1%).

We found most of the varieties to be partial restorers for the CMS lines of wild abortive (WA) and Kalinga I cytoplasmic sources. Aswathi, Punjab Basmati, and Ratna were found to be effective maintainers for Krishna A (Kalinga I); Aswathi, an effective restorer for Krishna A (WA); and Ratna, a partial restorer for Kiran A, Krishna A, Deepa A, and Madhuri A (WA).

Varieties IR9828-91-2-3 and Mahsuri were found to be effective restorers for 4 WA CMS lines (Kiran A, Madhuri A, Krishna A, or Deepa A) while they were partial restorers for Krishna A (Kalinga I) (see table). Like IR9828-91-2-3 and Mahsuri, Tetep was an effective restorer for Deepa A (WA), but a partial restorer for Krishna A (Kalinga I).

The variety Kalinga I was an effective restorer for CMS lines Krishna A (WA), Deepa A (WA), Madhuri A (WA), and Krishna A (Kalinga I) and a partial restorer for CMS line Kiran A (WA).

These findings indicate that the cytoplasm of Krishna A (Kalinga I source) may be different from that of Krishna A (WA) and other CMS lines of WA source. The behavior of a few varieties for the CMS lines from the same cytoplasmic source (WA) was sometimes different, possibly because of the nuclear and cytoplasmic interaction between the varieties and the CMS lines or the heterozygosity of the pollen parents. □

Restorer or maintainer reaction of elite lines in crosses with 5 CMS lines possessing WA and Kalinga I cytoplasm, 1991 dry season.^a

Male parent	Reaction of elite lines				
	Kiran A (WA)	Krishna A (WA)	Deepa A (WA)	Madhuri A (WA)	Krishna A (Kalinga I)
Annapurna	PR	PR	PR	PR	PR
ARC5961	-	-	-	-	PR
Archana	PR	-	-	-	-
Aswathi	-	R	-	-	M
Bhavani	-	-	-	-	WM
CR142-38	PR	PR	-	-	PR
CR386-9-3	-	-	-	WM	-
IR36	-	-	-	-	PR
IR9828-91-2-3	-	R	-	R	PR
Kalinga I	PR	R	R	R	R
Kranti	PR	-	-	-	PR
Kumar	-	-	-	R	-
Mahsuri	R	-	R	R	PR
Pokkali	PR	-	PR	PR	-
Ptb 10	-	-	-	-	WM
Punjab Basmati	-	-	-	-	M
Prakash	-	-	-	-	PR
Prasad	PR	-	-	-	-
Ratna	PR	PR	PR	PR	M
Tetep	-	-	R	-	PR
Vijaya	WM	PR	-	-	-

^aR = restorer, PR = partial restorer, WM = weak maintainer, and M = maintainer.